
Series: PHYSICS

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Supplementing the equations of Kepler's first law and the Mercury effect

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Abstract

It is proved that the equation of an elliptical orbit obtained taking into account the action of gravity can also be obtained taking into account the action of two forces - gravity and centrifugal force. It is shown that taking into account the centrifugal force allows us to justify the stability of elliptical orbits. This property of the new solution allows us to assert the reality of centrifugal force.

It is further shown that the satellite is affected by the Coriolis force, which creates a rotating moment of the satellite around the Sun. It is this moment that explains the Mercury effect. This fact allows us to assert the reality of the Coriolis force.

1. Centrifugal force acts on the satellite

The natural satellite revolves in an elliptical orbit around the Sun. This first law of Kepler follows analytically from Newton's laws of universal gravitation and inertial motion [1]. There is also centrifugal force (CFF). However, it is not used in the equations of celestial mechanics, since it is believed that CFF - this is one of the fictitious forces of inertia. The author has already proven that the CFF is a real force, the source of energy for which is the Earth's gravitational field [3, 4]. If we accept this statement, then Kepler's first law should be analytically derived taking into account the existence of the CF. The author made this analytical conclusion.

The known equations of motion of a satellite in an elliptical orbit in polar coordinates with the center of coordinates in the Sun have the form [1]:

$$\frac{\partial^2 r}{\partial t^2} = r \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} \right)^2 + F, \quad (1)$$

$$r^2 \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = (\vec{r} \times \vec{v}), \quad (2)$$

The equations taking into account the existence of the centralized system have the following form (see appendix):

$$\frac{\partial^2 r}{\partial t^2} = Z \sin^2(\theta - u) + F, \quad (3)$$

where

$$F = -GM/r^2, \quad (4)$$

$$Z = \frac{v^2}{r}, \quad (5)$$

r, θ - polar coordinates of radius,

v, u - polar coordinates of velocity,

F - specific central force,

Z - specific centrifugal force,

M - the mass of the Sun,

G - gravitational constant.

So there are two possible ways to describe a satellite's orbit, and both lead to the same result. But which equation does nature use?

Let's consider the specific force of the type

$$A = r \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} \right)^2. \quad (6)$$

The appendix and calculation example show that

$$A = Z = \frac{v^2}{r}, \quad (7)$$

$$F \neq \frac{v^2}{r}. \quad (8)$$

It is important to note that these relations are obtained from known formulas. From (6, 8) it follows that

$$r \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} \right)^2 = \frac{v^2}{r}. \quad (9)$$

Thus, the centripetal force is defined by (6) and is NOT equal to the force of gravitational attraction. There is a centrifugal force equal to the centripetal force.

2. Stability of an elliptical orbit

The satellite experiences random disturbances. We will not consider disturbances caused by the influence of celestial bodies on each other. But even a single satellite experiences disturbances that constantly exist. Indeed, Kepler's law is valid for point or spherical objects. But the planet is a shapeless lump, not a perfect sphere. Even if there are no external disturbances, there must be disturbances caused by the rotation of the planet around its own axis. It is obvious that a satellite that accidentally deviates from the ideal trajectory towards the Sun will be deviated even more by the increasing force of gravity. It is obvious that a satellite that accidentally exceeds its speed will not be slowed down by anything and will move to another orbit.

It has been proven (see, for example, [2]) that if these disturbances do not exceed a certain limit, then the planet oscillates around a constant orbit. This regularity has been verified by numerous computational experiments, and theorems describing these regularities have been obtained.

But why is the next random perturbation on average zero (as assumed in the theorems mentioned)?

But why are random disturbances limited and do not lead to a change in orbit for centuries?

But why doesn't the planet continue to rotate along the other elliptical path that the random disturbance pushed it onto?

It can be argued that the elliptical orbit is unstable.

To estimate the stability of the orbit using the new equation, let us consider how the central forces F and Z change when a random action changes the current radius by the value Δr . Figure 1 shows the graphs of the dependence of these forces on Δr . The point $\Delta r = 0$ corresponds to the condition $Z \approx F$, which is satisfied for a point located in an ideal orbit. When $\Delta r > 0$ the force F decreases in absolute value faster than the force Z , and the resulting force is directed toward the center, when $\Delta r < 0$ the resulting force is directed away from the center. Thus, when the radius of the satellite changes externally in one direction or another from the position in the ideal orbit, a force appears directed along the radius in the opposite direction - the satellite returns to the ideal orbit.

This means that the elliptical orbit calculated by the new equation is stable. Thus, the observed stability of the orbits indicates that the satellites are moved by gravity and centrifugal force. This, in turn, proves the reality of centrifugal force.

Fig. 1.

3. The Coriolis force acts on the satellite

It is known that there is slow precession of the perihelion of the orbit of Mercury, open Urbain Le Verrier in 1859, and the less noticeable precessions of the orbits of Mars, Venus and Earth, which were discovered by Simon Newcomb back in the century before last. It can be assumed that similar orbital shifts exist for all satellites. There is no explanation for such shifts within the framework of classical mechanics.

In addition to the above, a planet that rotates around its own axis and moves around the Sun is also affected by the specific Coriolis force [4]:

$$\bar{K} = -2(\bar{\omega} \times \bar{v}), \quad (10)$$

where $\bar{\omega}$ - the vector of the angular velocity of the satellite's rotation. Let us first consider the case when the vectors $\bar{v}$ and $\bar{\omega}$ are perpendicular. In this case, the vector $\bar{K}$ lies in the plane of the orbit and

$$K = -2\omega v. \quad (11)$$

The force $\bar{K}$ creates an acceleration directed along the plane of the orbit and perpendicular to the trajectory. This case applies to the motion of Mercury, since its axis of rotation is directed almost perpendicular to the plane of the orbit. In addition, Mercury has $\omega = 2 \cdot 10^{-7}$, which greatly exceeds the value of this quantity for all planets except Venus.

The rotational moment of a satellite around the Sun, created by the Coriolis force, is equal to

$$B = Kr\sin(n) \tag{12}$$

- see Fig. 2. In this case

$$k = u - \frac{\pi}{4} - \theta, \tag{12}$$

$$k = \theta + \frac{\pi}{4} - n. \tag{12}$$

Hence,

$$B = Kr\sin\left(u - \frac{\pi}{2} - 2\theta\right). \tag{13}$$

For example, the total torque created during one revolution of Mercury around the Sun is

$$B = 7 \cdot 10^8 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}. \tag{13}$$

If the vector $\bar{\omega}$ is directed along the plane of the orbit, then the force $\bar{K}$ will create a shift of the orbital plane relative to the center of the Sun.

These effects apparently exist on all planets.

Fig. 2.

4. Appendix

The orbital trajectory of the satellite in polar coordinates is:

$$\frac{\partial^2 r}{\partial t^2} = r \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t}\right)^2 + F, \tag{1}$$

$$r^2 \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = L, \tag{2}$$

$$L = (\bar{r} \times \bar{v}), \tag{3}$$

$$F = -GM/r^2, \tag{4}$$

where

- r, θ are polar coordinates with the center of coordinates in the Sun,
- v, u are polar coordinates of the satellite's speed,
- F is specific central force,
- L is specific angular momentum that is conserved in the field of central forces,
- M is the mass of the Sun,
- G is gravitational constant

Let's also consider the specific centrifugal force

$$Z = \frac{v^2}{r}. \quad (5)$$

Note that in our case

$$(\vec{r} \times \vec{v}) = r \cdot v \cdot \sin(\varphi), \quad (6)$$

where φ is the angle between the vectors $\vec{r}$ and $\vec{v}$, and

$$\varphi = \theta - u, \quad (7)$$

where u is the angle of inclination of the vector $\vec{v}$ – see Fig. 2. From (3, 6, 7) we find

$$L = rv \sin(\theta - u), \quad (8)$$

and from (5, 8) we obtain

$$L = r\sqrt{Zr} \sin(\theta - u). \quad (9)$$

Then from (2, 9, 5) we find:

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = \sqrt{\frac{Z}{r}} \sin(\theta - u) = \frac{v}{r} \sin(\theta - u). \quad (10)$$

Let's combine equations (1, 10):

$$\frac{\partial^2 r}{\partial t^2} = Z \sin^2(\theta - u) + F. \quad (11)$$

Thus, we have obtained a system of equations equivalent to the system of equations (1-4), of the form

$$\frac{\partial^2 r}{\partial t^2} = Z \sin^2(\theta - u) + F, \quad (11)$$

$$F = -GM/r^2, \quad (4)$$

$$Z = \frac{v^2}{r}. \quad (5)$$

5. Calculation example

Let us consider an example of calculating the motion of Mercury – see Fig. 3, which shows graphs of various functions depending on the x coordinate. The rectangular coordinates x, y and the ellipsoid of Mercury's rotation are also shown in Fig. 2. The parameters of Mercury's orbit were used in the calculation.

The following functions are shown in Fig. 3:

r, θ are polar coordinates with the center of coordinates in the Sun;
the formula used was

$$r = p(1 + \varepsilon \cos(\theta + \pi) + \varepsilon^2);$$

v, u are polar coordinates of the satellite's speed; the formula used
in this

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{GM}{p}(1 + 2\varepsilon \cos(\theta) + \varepsilon^2)};$$

F is specific central force (4),

L is specific angular momentum – see (3) in the appendix,

Z is specific centrifugal force, determined by (5),

A is specific centripetal force, determined by (6),

$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t}$ is the derivative of the angle θ , designated in Fig. 3 as $f1$ and $f1a$,
where $f1$ is calculated according to (1), and $f1a$ is calculated
according to (10) from the appendix,

$\frac{\partial^2 r}{\partial t^2}$ is the derivative calculated according to (1) and designated in Fig.
3 as $r2$.

It is important to note that only known formulas are used in the calculation, the force Z is calculated additionally. It is clear that formula (1) and formula (3) from the appendix coincide. It is also clear that formulas (5) and (6) coincide. Thus, the calculations show that

$$A = Z = \frac{v^2}{r}. \quad (1)$$

In addition, calculations show that the values F and Z differ by an average of 20%, i.e.

$$F \neq Z \text{ or } F \neq \frac{v^2}{r}. \quad (2)$$

It is important to note that these ratios are derived from known formulas.

Fig. 3.

Refereces

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